

Assessing the cooking stability and prebiotic potential of flaxseed mucilage

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Highlights

- Flaxseed is rich in essential nutrients such as protein, lipids, minerals and carbohydrates
- Flaxseed carbohydrates (or mucilage) have prebiotic properties and support growth of some lactobacilli and bifidobacteria
- Flaxseed mucilage does not lose its prebiotic properties at normal cooking conditions

1: Background

Flaxseed (*Linum usitatissimu*) has become a well-known functional food ingredient due to the high levels of dietary fibre [1,2]. This abundant source is found in the mucilage of flaxseed and has been determined for their prebiotic properties [3]. Nevertheless, the stability of this carbohydrate under normal cooking conditions has not been investigated. Due to its nature, the cooking parameters such as temperature (hot and cold; dry and wet), time and pH (ie., alkaline, acidic and neutral) are expected to have some effects (ie., degradation) on the structure which can result in the changes of prebiotic behaviour of dietary fibre in flaxseed mucilage.

2: Objective

To study the ability of flaxseed mucilage to support the growth of the gut bacteria, and assess the effects of cooking conditions (temperature and pH) on the prebiotic properties of the mucilage.

3: Methods

4: Results

Fig 1: Growth of *B. longum* subsp. *longum* ATCC 15707t on treated flax mucilage; BM: basal medium; NT: non-treated mucilage

Fig 3: Growth of *L. ruminis* DSM 27781 on treated flax mucilage; BM: basal medium; NT: non-treated mucilage

Fig 2: Growth of *B. adolescentis* DSM 20083t on treated flax mucilage; BM: basal medium; NT: non-treated mucilage

Fig 4: Growth of *L. acidophilus* ATCC 4356t on treated flax mucilage; BM: basal medium; NT: non-treated mucilage

5: Conclusion

- Higher temperatures promoted the easy dissolution of mucilage in water
- pH affected the colour of reconstituted mucilage; mucilage appeared brighter at acidic pH and 'darker' at basic pH
- pH- and temperature-treated mucilage retained their ability to support growth of gut bacteria.
- Among the bacteria tested, *B. longum*, and *L. ruminis* were able to grow better on mucilage.
- General levels of growth for all bacteria tested were low, probably due to the complex molecular structure of the mucilage polysaccharides.

6: Future studies

- Reduce complex molecular structure of mucilage polysaccharides via hydrolysis with acid or enzymes into oligomers before screening for ability to support bacteria growth

7. Acknowledgment

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8. References

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